

Design and Analysis of Novel Unit Cell Structures

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Abstract—This paper presents the design and analysis of novel-shaped unit-cell structures for reflectarray antennas, including triangular torus, crescent-shaped, magnifying lens, tri-circle, and butterfly patches. The unit-cells are designed to operate in the Ku-band (12–18 GHz), with a center frequency of 15 GHz. To investigate the scattering characteristics of the proposed unit-cells, full-wave simulations were conducted using CST Microwave Studio, a commercially available electromagnetic simulation tool. The reflection coefficients and phase responses of each resonant element are analyzed and discussed. The results demonstrate and compare the performance of the five unit-cell designs. All elements exhibit a wide phase tuning range of 360 degrees, confirming their potential for efficient reflectarray applications.

Index Terms—Ku-band, Phase, reflectarray, tuning, unit-cell

I. INTRODUCTION

Long-distance communication systems require high-gain antennas [1]. Traditionally, such applications have relied on parabolic reflectors and antenna arrays. However, manufacturing parabolic reflectors becomes increasingly complex at higher frequencies due to their curved geometries. Furthermore, parabolic antennas inherently lack wide-angle beam-scanning capabilities.

Conversely, high-gain phased arrays can achieve extensive beam scanning but are typically complex and costly to implement. To address these challenges, the concept of the reflectarray has been developed [2], combining the advantages of both parabolic reflectors and phased arrays [3]. Reflectarray antennas offer several benefits [4], including a low-profile form factor and reduced fabrication costs. Their compact structure [5][6] makes them more portable than traditional bulky parabolic dishes. Typically, a reflectarray comprises a horn feed antenna and an array of radiating elements [7]. Due to the spatial illumination from the horn, there are inherent path and phase differences across the array elements, which must be compensated by tuning [8] the resonant dimensions of each element.

Over time, numerous geometries for the unit-cell

elements have been proposed to achieve diverse phase ranges and polarization characteristics [9]. This work focuses on the design and analysis of novel unit-cell structures [10] [11] for reflectarray antennas. The proposed designs target satellite communication applications, operating within the Ku-band frequency range (12–18 GHz) [12], commonly used for satellite broadcasting and data links.

A micro strip reflectarray antenna consists of a thin reflective surface with printed array elements, illuminated by a feed antenna positioned in front of it. The radiated waves from the feed interact with these elements and are re-radiated to produce a planar phase front. However, because the central elements have a shorter path length to the feed compared to the corner elements, it is necessary to compensate for these differences to achieve a uniform phase front.

Reflectarrays thus combine the benefits of parabolic reflectors, which produce high-gain planar waves from a focal feed, with the steerability of phased arrays. While parabolic reflectors maintain high gain [13], their performance depends on accurately positioning the feed at the focal point, which is often challenging [14]. On the other hand, phased arrays use individually powered elements with electronically controlled phase shifting to form steerable, highly directional beams, though at the cost of increased complexity and expense.

In designing micro strip reflectarrays [15], a critical factor is achieving a sufficiently wide phase range and a gradual phase slope relative to the element size. A slower phase variation reduces sensitivity to manufacturing tolerances, offering greater flexibility in choosing element dimensions for specific phase values. A restricted phase range can lead to phase approximation errors and truncated phase shifts, potentially causing intersymbol interference (ISI) in digitally modulated signals. Therefore, investigating phase behavior across the operating frequency band is essential.

For applications such as personal mobile communications [16] and satellite systems, compact micro strip antennas [17] are often desired. To meet these requirements, modifications to conventional micro strip patch antennas [18] are necessary to realize smaller, higher-frequency structures

[19] [20]. One strategy involves combining triangular and crescent-shaped patches into novel structures such as magnifying lens patches, tri-circles, and butterfly shapes.

This paper presents the design and analysis of novel unit-cell reflectarray geometries for operation within the Ku-band (12–18 GHz). Reflection coefficient and phase characteristics were evaluated using CST Microwave Studio, demonstrating that these novel structures achieve a 360-degree phase range, making them suitable for high-performance reflectarray antenna applications.

II. DESIGN

The scattering characteristics of the unit-cell have been studied and analyzed using CST Microwave Studio, a commercially available electromagnetic simulation software based on the Finite Integration Technique (FIT) and employing the Floquet (infinite periodic) approach. Each unit-cell is investigated individually, with appropriate boundary conditions applied, and the excitation is achieved through a plane wave.

Designing a reflectarray antenna generally involves a two-step process [4]. The first step is a parametric study of the unit-cell to identify and optimize the relevant control parameters, including its shape, thickness, and other geometric features [5]. Upon completion of this step, the designer gains control over the critical parameters, enabling the achievement of the desired antenna performance.

Phase characterization of the unit-cells can be carried out using various techniques. In this work, an infinite array approach is adopted. Phase variation among the unit-cells is essential, since each cell experiences a different distance from the feed source, resulting in differing phase delays. Several phase compensation strategies are available for achieving the required phase distribution, such as varying the substrate parameters, adjusting rotation angles, modifying patch sizes, altering stub lengths, or introducing slots of variable size on the ground plane.

A. Design of unit cells

CST Microwave Studio has been utilized as a simulation tool to model the unit-cell of the reflectarray antenna, employing the Finite Integration Technique (FIT) method. The careful selection of the type and geometry of the reflective element, as well as the substrate properties, is critical to achieving the desired performance. In this study, an FR4-lossy substrate with a thickness of 1.6 mm and a relative permittivity (ϵ_r) of 4.3 was chosen, backed by a conducting ground plane.

For the characterization of the unit-cell reflectarray, the two most significant parameters are the reflection loss and the reflection phase [6]. The figures below illustrate the novel patch designs and their simulated outputs, showing reflection loss and reflection phase within the Ku-band frequency range of 12–18 GHz, with a center frequency of 15 GHz.

The bandwidth performance of the reflectarray antennas is analyzed based on the reflection loss curves. Bandwidth

is defined as the frequency range exceeding 10% above the maximum reflection loss value. The designed unit-cells achieve a phase range of exactly 360°. Additionally, all proposed patches demonstrate good return loss values, specifically:

- Triangular torus patch: -22 dB
- Crescent patch: -40 dB
- Magnifying lens patch: -45 dB
- Tri-circle patch: -10 dB
- Butterfly patch: -41 dB

The comparison of reflection phase performance is quantified using the Figure of Merit (FOM) and the static phase range. The FOM is defined as the rate of change of the reflection phase with respect to return loss.

$$FOM = \Delta\phi / \text{Return loss in (dB)} \quad (1)$$

Table I summarizes the linear phase range, reflection loss, and figure of merit for the proposed unit-cell designs.

TABLE I RESULTS OF DESIGNED UNIT-CELLS

Resonant Elements	Reflection Loss (dB)	Phase Range	FOM(°/ GHz)
Triangled Torus Patch	-22	360°	16.36
Crescents Patch	-40	360°	9
Magnifying Lens Patch	-45	360°	8
Tri-circle Patch	-10	360°	36
Butterfly Patch	-41	360°	8.8

i)Triangled Torus Patch

Fig.1. Triangled Torus Patch

ii) Crescents patch

Fig. 2. Crescents patch

Fig. 5. Butterfly Patch

iii) Magnifying Lens patch

Fig. 3. Magnifying lens patch

iv) Tricircle patch

Fig. 4. Tricircle patch

v) Butterfly Patch

B. Analysis of simulation results

Fig. 6 and Fig.7 of Triangled torus patch shows the frequency shift which is less compared to other patch's results. The other graphs show the gradual frequency shift by sweeping the patch dimensions such as radius and length of the stub line. Fig. 8 and Fig. 9 of crescent patch, Fig. 10 and Fig. 11 of magnifying lens patch, Fig. 12 and Fig. 13 of tricircle patch, Fig. 14 and Fig. 15 of butterfly patch shows the good frequency shift and they are good candidates for reflectarray design.

Fig.6. Reflection loss vs frequency

Fig.7. Reflection phase vs frequency

Fig. 8. Reflection loss vs frequency

Fig. 11. Reflection phase vs frequency

Fig. 9. Reflection Phase vs frequency

Fig. 12. Reflection loss vs frequency

Fig. 10. Reflection loss vs frequency

Fig. 13. Reflection phase vs frequency

Fig. 14. Reflection loss vs frequency

Fig. 15. Reflection phase vs frequency

III. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

All elements are suitable reflectarray candidates due to their 360° phase range and high reflection performance. Among them, the magnifying lens and crescent patches offer the best reflection loss while maintaining moderate FOM, suggesting they may balance efficiency and phase performance effectively. The tri-circle patch has the highest FOM, indicating it is potentially more phase-agile but could be more challenging to fabricate with stable performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

The design and analysis of unit-cell structures incorporating various radiating element geometries have been presented. Simulation results indicate that all five proposed patch shapes achieve a full 360° phase reflection range. However, they exhibit relatively narrow bandwidths compared to other conventional elements, which can be attributed to the reduced effective reflecting area of the resonant elements. Despite this, these geometries demonstrate high reflection parameters suggesting their potential as effective reflectors in reflectarray antenna applications. Among all the patches, Tricircle patch with inset feeding gives high Figure of merit and S curve is smooth compared to all other patches. Next, triangular torus patch performs well. The other patches are equally

performing. So, we can go for constructing array with these results.

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